

Calotoc and Ketan Nangka(KN)/IR36 // Kamairazu and tested the *Est9* isozyme marker (chromosome 7). Isozyme analyses were conducted according to methods reported by Ishikawa et al (1989) and Glaszmann et al (1989). The morphological fertility of pollen was determined by staining pollen grains in 1% I₂KI solution. Round, stained pollen grains were determined to be morphologically fertile, while the small, undyed pollen grains were sterile.

In the F₂ lines of KN / IR36 // Kamairazu, the morphological fertility of pollen was clearly differentiated by marker genotypes *Est9-12* and *Est9-11*, which were derived from IR36 / Kamairazu and KN / Kamairazu, respectively (see table). This result suggests the existence of a locus for determining pollen fertility in the morphological sense. The locus may be located near

Distribution of morphological fertility of pollen classified by marker genotypes in KN/IR36//Kamairazu and Akihikari//IR36/Calotoc.

Genotype*	Plants with morphological fertility (%)								Total	Mean (%)	Probability
	<i>KN/IR36//Kamairazu</i>										
	40	50	60	70	80	90	100				
<i>Est9-12</i>	0	2	6	2	0	1	2	13	62.2		
<i>Est9-11</i>	0	1	0	2	1	5	9	18	85.1	<0.01	
	<i>Akihikari//IR36/Calotoc</i>										
<i>Est9-12</i>	1	1	1	2	1	4	1	11	71.5		
<i>Est9-11</i>				2	1	2	5	10	83.4	0.05-0.10	

the *Est9* with an approximate recombination value of 0.19 ± 0.13 . In Akihikari // IR36 / Calotoc, the same result was obtained (see table), and an approximate recombination value between the locus and *Est9* was estimated to be 0.19 ± 0.17 .

A gamete abortion gene *galla* which gave a recombination value of 0.23 with

Est9 on chromosome 7 has been reported.

The locus for pollen fertility indicated here by the isozyme marker *Est9* may be identical to *gall1*, where sterile pollens were produced on heterozygotes at the locus near *gall1* on chromosome 7. A neutral allele, named *galln* at the locus *gall1*, was identified by this study. ■

Correlation and heritability of grain and leaf characters in indica rice in high yield-conducive environments of Yunnan, China

Zeng Yawen, Chen Yong, and Liao Xinhua, Crop Germplasm Resources Station, Yunnan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Kunming 650205, China

China has bred 15 cultivars, including Guichao 2 and Yue 517, whose yields have exceeded 15 t ha⁻¹ with single

cropping of middle rice in the Jing-shajiang region (e.g., Yuanmou, Yongsheng), because of favorable climatic conditions: annual mean air temperature, 17.9-21.9°C; >10°C cumulative temperature, 5954.1-7986.0°C; >18°C accumulated temperature, 4126-6050°C; annual sunshine, 2179.4-2736.0 h; annual rainfall, 449.6-801.2 mm; annual evaporation of 2636-3820 mm is 3.4-6.0 times rainfall; and relative humidity, 54-64%. During the rice cropping season, about 5 mo from April to August, the >10°C cumulative

temperature is 3822.4-4100.0°C. For example, single cropping of middle rice at Taoyuan township in Yunnan Province requires a cumulative temperature of 1050°C from sowing to transplanting, 2150°C from transplanting to full heading, 880°C from full heading to maturation, and rainfall from 411.5 to 424.4 mm. Yield components (15-17 t ha⁻¹) were 4,710,000±103.5 panicles ha⁻¹, 133±28.6 grains panicle⁻¹, and 27.6±2.3 g 1000-grain weight⁻¹. Fertilizer is applied heavily at early stages, lightly at middle stages, and supplementary at

Heritability (H), heritability ratio (Hr), and coefficients of genetic correlation (r) for kernel and leaf traits.^a

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
A	63.0	84.9	84.78	66.88	58.21	86.27	78.10	24.12	80.53	91.99	67.54	95.23
B	0.527**	79.2	47.39	45.21	89.73	86.21	78.10	75.37	74.75	88.55	78.39	97.23
C	0.902**		0.848**	58.6	46.58	66.45	86.81	79.87	89.29	72.15	88.07	
D	0.670**	0.969**	0.880**	75.3	88.37	83.82	63.50	82.66	67.76	81.53	76.59	98.46
E	0.763**	0.033	0.630**	0.169	98.5	99.70	98.14	98.77	89.76	89.54	84.88	93.81
F	-0.311	0.394	-0.206	0.336	-0.763**	98.3	85.22	72.76	58.16	81.44	88.73	
G	0.526**	0.679**	0.556**	0.796**	0.031	0.588**	96.2	85.77	73.59	73.19	77.60	91.87
H	0.728**	0.145	-0.506**	0.053	-0.876**	0.479	0.134	68.9	45.91	83.03	75.08	51.00
I	-0.452	0.155	0.174	0.084	-0.569**	0.827**	0.243	0.662**	70.1	79.80	70.74	85.59
J	0.373	0.127	-0.306	0.061	-0.866**	0.908**	0.385	0.887**	0.792**	78.4	81.31	68.80
K	0.069	0.675**	0.286	0.541	-0.352	0.297	0.262	0.413**	-0.046	0.399**	79.5	75.78
L	-0.716**	0.014	-0.604**	-0.430	-0.813**	0.417**	0.016	0.918**	0.419	0.821**	0.422	87.2

^a*,**= significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 level of P, respectively. A=flag leaf length, B=flag leaf width, C=2 penultimate leaf length, D=2 penultimate leaf width, E=grain length, F=grain width, G=1000-grain weight, H=filled grains panicle⁻¹, I=spikelets panicle⁻¹, J=grain weight panicle⁻¹, K=grain weight plant⁻¹, L=yield ha⁻¹.

late stages (207.0 kg N ha⁻¹, 65.3 kg P ha⁻¹, 124.5 kg K ha⁻¹) combined with increased foliar spray.

We studied genetic correlation and heritability for a trait defined as a ratio of two kernel-leaf characters in eight high-yielding rice cultivars. A randomized block design with three replications in 10.0-m² plots of medium soil were laid out at Yuanmou (elevation 118.4 m) under high-yield ecology and conventional management in Yunnan during the 1994 season.

The heritability of each character, a ratio of two component traits, and their genetic correlation for the means of 12 traits, were calculated (see table). The results showed that kernel characters had higher heritability than leaf characters, especially grain length (8.5%), grain width (98.3%), and grain per width (99.7%). Because the >10°C cumulative temperature was 3993.7 °C and rainfall was 424.4 mm during the rice cropping season in Yuanmou, climatic conditions were advantageous to full expression of kernel character inheritance in indica rice. Heritability of >90% included grain length/grain width (99.7%), grain length/filled grain width / yield ha⁻¹ (98.5%), grain length / 1000-grain weight (98.1%), flag leaf width/ yield ha⁻¹ (97.2%), flag leaf length/yield ha⁻¹ (95.3%), grain length/ yield ha⁻¹ (93.8%), grain width/100-grain weight (93.7%), flag leaf length/ grain weight panicle⁻¹ (92.0%), and 1000-grain weight /yield ha⁻¹ (91.9%). The ratio of kernel-leaf characters showed high heritability, especially grain length/width under the high-yield ecology of Yunnan. Yield ha⁻¹ was positively and significantly correlated with filled grains panicle⁻¹ (r=0.918), grain weight plant⁻¹ (r=0.821), grain width (r=0.471), grain weight plant⁻¹ (r=0.422), and spikelets panicle⁻¹ (r=0.419). A high-yielding cultivar should have medium width and short flag leaf, short and round kernel, moderate 1000-grain weight, and increased kernel number and grain weight panicle⁻¹. ■

Heterosis: early prediction and relationship with reproductive phase

C. H. M. Vijayakumar, M. I. Ahmed, B. C. Viraktamath, and M. S. Ramesha, Hybrid Rice Laboratory, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

We studied the relationship between reproductive phase and heterosis and looked for traits affecting heterosis. In the 1994 wet season at the International Hybrid Rice Observational Nursery (IRHON), 24 hybrids and their respective restorers (one plant each) were dissected to identify the initiation of reproductive phase marked by the formation of a hairy structure. Similarly in the 1995 wet season, three to five plants each from 20 hybrids and their 20 restorers were dissected. At maturity grain yield m⁻² and observations on several yield components in five selected plants were recorded as well as

days to 50% flowering for each hybrid and restorer (Table 1). Reproductive phase initiation occurred early in hybrids. Restorer yield in parents was higher than maintainer yield in all hybrid combinations. We found a definite, positive relation between better parent (restorer) heterosis and reproductive phase duration. (Table 1). In the H>R group, reproductive phase duration of hybrids was extended with no change in growth duration (days to 50% flowering). In group H<R, days to 50% flowering of hybrids was early compared with restorers but was unaccompanied by a change in reproductive phase duration.

Table 2 compares yield and yield components of hybrids and restorers. The yield superiority of hybrids or restorers was positively related to plant height. The number of filled spikelets was always high in hybrids. Hybrids possessed higher values for most yield traits than restorers, except in group H<R of IR62829A-based hybrids. The

Table 1. Relationship between reproductive phase duration and heterosis. Andhra Pradesh, India. 1994-95.

Season	Hybrids (no.)	Particulars	Reproductive phase initiation	Days to 50% flowering	Difference	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)
1994 WS	15	H>R:Hybrid	79 ^a	107	28 ^a	641 ^a
		:Restorer	86	109	23	509
	9	H<R:Hybrid	82 ^a	106 ^a	24	474 ^a
		:Restorer	88	110	22	583
1995 WS	8	H>R:Hybrid	64 ^a	95	31 ^a	624 ^a
		:Restorer	68	94	25	491
	12	H<R:Hybrid	64 ^a	90 ^a	26	473 ^a
		:Restorer	69	96	27	569
IR58025A-based hybrids	5	H>R:Hybrid	64 ^a	96	32	644 ^a
		:Restorer	72	96	24	473
		:IR58025B	70	93	23	323
	8	:Hybrid	66 ^a	92 ^a	26	458 ^a
		H<R:Restorer	71	97	26	577
		:IR58025B	70	93	23	323
IR62829A-based hybrids	3	:Hybrid	63	92	29 ^a	591
		H>R:Restorer	63	89	26	520
		:IR62828B	62	87	25	435
	4	:Hybrid	59	86	27	503 ^a
		H<R:Restorer	65	93	28	552
		:IR62829B	62	87	25	435

^a P=0.05.